

A Feasibility Study on Opportunistic Tropospheric Sensing for Meteorological and Geophysical Applications using Microwave Satellite Downlinks

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Abstract—The propagation of microwaves through the lower atmosphere is significantly influenced by various components, the main ones being atmospheric gases, weather phenomena and suspended particles (e.g., ash and gases released in the atmosphere by volcanic emissions). While the first two have been widely investigated and characterized (see, e.g., the relevant ITU-R recommendations), only a few studies are available about the effects of the latter one on microwave communication links. In recent years, the opportunistic use of satellite downlinks emerged as a promising and cost-effective technique for the detection and quantitative characterization of weather phenomena (mainly, the precipitations). This work leverages on the experience earned on weather sensing to extend the opportunistic approach also to real-time detection and monitoring of volcanic emissions, with a twofold aim: i) to understand the impact of volcanic emissions on microwave signals propagation; ii) to assess the feasibility of an opportunistic system for volcanic activity sensing, based on the monitoring of satellite downlink signals.

Index Terms—Opportunistic sensing, Microwave propagation, Volcanic ash, Geophysical measurements, Satellite ground stations.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE propagation of microwave signals (i.e., at frequencies above 1 GHz) through the lower atmosphere (0–12 km) is influenced by atmospheric gases, various weather phenomena, and suspended particles [1]. All of these tropospheric components cause absorption, reflection and scattering effects of the electromagnetic radiation at micro-physical level. The key parameter to assess the impact of tropospheric components on microwave propagation is the specific attenuation, which quantifies the resulting signal strength reduction per unit distance, and is customarily expressed in dB/km (see also ITU-R Recommendations [2], [3]).

A. State-of-the-Art of Opportunistic Sensing for Meteorology

In recent years, microwave communication links, such as the downlinks of communication satellites, have been considered as opportunity signal sources for tropospheric sensing. Such an “opportunistic” approach emerged as a very promising, reliable and cost-effective technique for

the detection and quantitative characterization of weather components, especially precipitations [4]. The opportunistic use of existing communication satellite infrastructures for weather sensing, as shown in Fig. 1a, is nowadays a well established and extensively tested unconventional technique that uses low-cost commercial-grade satellite receivers to extract valuable meteorological data from the received signals, and can effectively complement conventional weather sensor networks [5].

For example, a network of satellite terminals for opportunistic rain sensing has been deployed in Central Italy as part of the NEFOCAST [6] and INSIDERAIN [7] projects. Another set of satellite sensors were installed in some European coastal cities within the activities of the SCORE [8] project. Experimental results from opportunistic sensors have been eventually validated by comparing them with measurements obtained from conventional meteorological instruments, demonstrating good accuracy of precipitation estimates [9].

B. Potential of Opportunistic Sensing for Geophysics

By leveraging on the experience earned on weather sensing, the goal of this work is to extend the opportunistic approach also to geophysical applications. More specifically, we focus here on real-time monitoring of volcanic emissions, which is crucial for improving early warning systems and also for understanding the impact of volcanic activity on both local and global atmospheric dynamics. Considering that volcanic eruptions release vast amounts of ash and gases into the atmosphere, our aim hereafter is twofold: i) to understand the impact of volcanic emissions on microwave signals propagation; ii) to assess the feasibility of an opportunistic sensing system based on satellite downlink signals for detection and monitoring of volcanic activity, as shown in Fig. 1b.

II. OVERVIEW OF CHEMICAL COMPONENTS IN VOLCANIC EMISSIONS

The fragmentation of magma and parts of the volcanic system, through which the magma passes, generates solid particles that are collectively known as pyroclasts (or

Fig. 1. Opportunistic sensing systems based on satellite downlink signals, for rain (a) and volcanic (b) monitoring.

tephra), and consist predominantly of fragmented volcanic glass, mineral crystals, and rock fragments. Together with volcanic gases and entrained atmospheric air, they form the major constituents of a volcanic plume [10]. The composition and the physical properties of volcanic pyroclasts and gases significantly varies depending on many factors such as the type of volcano, the composition of the magma, and the processes occurring during the eruption. The temperature and pressure of an eruption further influence the composition of the volcanic emissions. High-temperature and low-viscosity magmas tend to release gas more gradually, while more viscous magmas retain gas until pressure becomes sufficient to cause a violent explosion [11].

A. Volcanic Solid Particles

The diameter of volcanic particles in fall deposits typically ranges from a few microns or less, to several centimeters or more. It decreases with distance from the vent, as larger particles tend to fall out quickly [12]. In the literature, solid particles of a volcanic cloud are commonly classified into three main categories, based on the particle size, as follows: i) ash, ii) lapilli, and iii) block. For each of them, Tab. I summarizes the typical diameters of the particles, the residence periods in the atmosphere, and the distance from the vent that volcanic debris can reach.

Many studies in the literature have focused primarily on

the characterization of volcanic ash due to its substantial impact on microwave signals [13], [14], [15], [16]. Volcanic ash is known to affect microwave propagation primarily because of its longer residence times in the atmosphere compared to other atmospheric particles. This characteristic leads to a greater likelihood of interaction with microwave frequencies, making it a critical area of study for assessing potential hazards. Volcanic ashes are formed by volcanoes through several different processes that transform large batches of magma and country rock into smaller pieces [17].

The concentration of ash within a volcanic plume is often reported in terms of mass per unit volume (e.g., g/m^3 or mg/m^3), with values varying considerably depending on factors such as the eruption's intensity, distance from the eruption source and environmental conditions [18]. At high concentrations near the eruption vent, ash particles may reach several grams per cubic meter, creating dense clouds with the potential to blanket surrounding areas with thick layers of ash. However, ash concentrations diminish rapidly due to particle fallout and atmospheric dispersion, often decreasing to milligrams, or even micrograms, per cubic meter within a few hundred kilometers [19].

B. Volcanic Gases

Volcanic gases released during eruptions play a critical role in atmospheric chemistry, climate modulation, and

TABLE I
MAIN CHARACTERISTICS OF VOLCANIC PYROCLASTS (FROM [13]).

Tephra	Particle type	Typical particle size	Distance from volcano vent	Atmospheric residence time
Ash	Fine Ash (FA)	< 0.064 mm	Hundreds to thousands of kilometers	Days to months or years
	Coarse Ash (CA)	0.064–0.532 mm	Tens to hundreds of kilometers	Days
Lapilli	Small Lapilli (SL)	0.532–2.56 mm	Few to tens of kilometers	Few minutes
	Large Lapilli (LL)	2.56–32 mm	Hundreds of meters to a few kilometers	Seconds to minutes
Blocks	Blocks and Bombs (BB)	> 32 mm	Tens to hundreds of meters	Tens of seconds

environmental health. Water vapor (H_2O) is the most abundant gas in volcanic emissions (often about 60-90% of the total gas emissions) and plays a fundamental role in magmatic processes, eruption dynamics, and atmospheric interactions. It originates from the mantle and subducted materials, and its release is closely tied to magma ascent and decompression processes [20]. Understanding and characterizing water vapor emissions is crucial for volcanic monitoring, hazard assessment, and improving predictive models of volcanic activity.

In addition to water vapor, volcanoes also emit several other gases, including carbon dioxide (CO_2), sulfur dioxide (SO_2), and smaller amounts, or traces, of gases like hydrogen sulfide (H_2S), hydrogen chloride (HCl), hydrogen fluoride (HF), and noble gases [21]. The total volume and composition of gases released depend on factors such as magma composition, type of eruption, and tectonic setting [10].

III. SATELLITE DOWNLINK FREQUENCIES AVAILABLE FOR OPPORTUNISTIC MEASUREMENTS

For opportunistic tropospheric sensing, it is advantageous to utilize existing signals that are already radiated through the atmosphere. To this respect, the Geostationary (GEO) broadcasting satellites are the preferred choice as they provide strong, stable, continuous (i.e., 24-hour), microwave downlink signals from fixed locations in the sky, over a large geographic area (nation- or continent-wide). Moreover, a large number of satellites are available on the GEO arc in the sky, in line-of-sight from the ground. For example, Figure 2 illustrates the arc of GEO satellites that are visible from Montelaguardia (Catania, Sicily, Italy) ($37.8740^\circ N$, $14.9949^\circ E$). This study primarily focuses on

Fig. 2. Arc in the sky of the GEO satellites in geometrical visibility in Montelaguardia (Catania, Sicily, Italy), ($37.8740^\circ N$, $14.9949^\circ E$).

satellites operating in Ku-band for television broadcasting in DVB-S2 (Digital Video Broadcasting via Satellite 2nd

generation) format. The signals transmitted by these satellites can be easily received using low-cost, commercial-grade satellite receivers, making content widely available and accessible. In Fig. 2, marked in red, are shown as an example, two of the most popular GEO satellite positions for television broadcasting in Europe. These satellites transmit strong signals, ensuring extensive coverage across the continent. The green markers show the broadcast satellites used for the experimental measurements carried out within the above mentioned NEFOCAST, INSIDERAIN, and SCORE projects. Additionally, there is a couple of satellites, indicated with blue markers, that operate at higher frequencies, in the Ka-band, and are therefore more susceptible to the attenuation caused by the atmospheric components. These are briefly outlined hereafter.

- Ka-Sat - It supports the Tooway™ service and offers satellite-based broadband Internet access with wide European coverage [22].
- Alphasat - It is an advanced satellite, primarily used for technological experimentation [23]. It hosts experimental payloads, including Ka-band beacons for signal propagation studies and the development of new technologies for future satellite missions. Since Alphasat is not designed for commercial services, it cannot be accessed with low-cost off-the-shelf receivers; instead, a dedicated receiving system must be purposely developed.

Fig. 3. Ground projections of microwave links from selected GEO satellites, in Montelaguardia (Catania, Sicily, Italy), ($37.8740^\circ N$, $14.9949^\circ E$).

Figure 3 illustrates the ground projections of the microwave links from some selected GEO satellites available for opportunistic measurements in Montelaguardia. The colors of the satellite links are the same as those used in Fig. 2. As shown, Montelaguardia is on the North side of the Mount Etna volcano and, since the satellite receiver faces southwards, it reveals a very favorable location for monitoring the emissions from the volcano. Table II summarizes the key characteristics of the satellite communication bands available for opportunistic measurements, including frequency ranges [24], types of services,

satellites, and types of receivers required to access the data. The band designations adhere to the terminology commonly used among the community of broadcasting engineers.

IV. SPECIFIC ATTENUATION FOR VOLCANIC COMPONENTS

This section presents an overview of specific attenuation values reported in the literature for the constituents of volcanic clouds, related to some major volcanic eruptions. Clearly, the actual extent of microwave attenuation depends on several factors such as the operating frequency and particles' size, chemical composition and concentration.

A. Volcanic Solid Particles

Volcanic solid particles significantly affect microwave propagation, primarily through absorption and scattering mechanisms [25]. Several studies on attenuation caused by volcanic ash particles indicate a significant reduction in signal strength across various microwave bands. Attenuation grows as the concentration of volcanic ash particles increases. In [14] the authors developed particle size distribution (PSD) models that simulate the specific attenuation (denoted as γ) as a function of the ash concentration (denoted as C_a) for 3 different frequency bands: S-, C- and X-band. These models were validated with radar data collected during real volcanic eruptions of Mount Saint Helens and Mount Etna volcanoes. In this study, we resorted to specific attenuation data from [14] (Fig. 4) and we developed a regression model in order to derive the attenuation values also for the Ku and Ka broadcasting bands that are considered for opportunistic measurements. This model accounts for various particle size classes, including fine and coarse ash, and lapilli. The results are shown in Fig. 4. The blue and red plots correspond to a volcanic particle concentration of 5 g/m^3 and 12.15 g/m^3 , respectively. The dots represent the experimental collected data, the solid lines are the linear regression model used to describe the relationship between frequency and specific attenuation, and the squares indicate the values extrapolated by the model for frequencies in Ku- and Ka-bands. The determination coefficient R^2 , whose values are summarized in Tab. III, indicates a good correlation between frequency and attenuation.

The results shown in Fig. 4 indicate that attenuation is greater in higher frequency bands compared to lower frequency bands. This is because, at higher frequencies, the wavelength becomes comparable to the size of volcanic particles. Specifically, at Ku- and Ka-band frequencies, the wavelengths are similar to the dimensions of lapilli. This results in a significant increase in attenuation due to greater scattering and absorption.

B. Volcanic Gases

The principal interaction mechanism involving the gaseous constituents and a radio wave is molecular absorption,

Fig. 4. Specific attenuation versus frequency, for two different concentrations of volcanic particles (C_{vp}), for Fine and Coarse Ash (a) and Lapilli (b).

which results in an amplitude reduction of the radio signal. The absorption of the radio wave results from a quantum level change in the rotational energy of the molecule, and occurs at a specific resonant frequency or narrow band of frequencies. The resonant frequency of interaction depends on the energy levels of the initial and final rotational energy states of the molecule [26]. Figure 5 shows the specific attenuation produced by water vapor in the atmosphere at 20°C surface temperature for different concentrations [2]. Focusing on the frequency band available for opportunistic measurements, it is important to note that water vapor exhibits an absorption line (due to a resonance frequency) around 22 GHz, i.e., in vicinity of the bands used for the downlink of satellite communication services.

The other volcanic gases outlined in Section II do not exhibit radiation absorption in the microwave bands of interest for this study: carbon dioxide (CO_2) absorbs infrared (IR) radiation at a variety of wavelengths in the range $2\text{--}15 \mu\text{m}$; sulfur dioxide (SO_2) absorbs IR radiation at $4 \mu\text{m}$ and $7.7\text{--}8.5 \mu\text{m}$; hydrogen sulfide (H_2S) absorbs ultraviolet (UV) radiation in the $190\text{--}230 \text{ nm}$ band, and it also weakly absorbs IR radiation; hydrogen chloride (HCl) absorbs IR radiation at $1.75 \mu\text{m}$, has also a series of peaks in the range $3.23\text{--}3.77 \mu\text{m}$ and absorbs UV radiation at 157 nm and 193 nm ; hydrogen fluoride (HF) absorbs radiation in the bands $1.26\text{--}1.35 \mu\text{m}$, $865\text{--}895 \text{ nm}$, and $2.34\text{--}2.82$

TABLE II
SATELLITE DOWNLINK FREQUENCY BANDS FOR OPPORTUNISTIC SENSING [24].

Band	Frequency Range	Type of Service	Satellite - Longitude	Type of Receiver
Ku	10.7 - 12.75 GHz	DVB-S2 (broadcasting)	Various (see Fig. 2)	Commercial
Ka	18.4 - 21.2 GHz	Tooway™ (internet access)	Ka-Sat - 9°E	Commercial
		Experimental communications	Alphasat - 25°E	Ad-hoc

TABLE III
DETERMINATION COEFFICIENT FOR THE PREDICTED MODEL.

Particle type	Determination Coefficient (R^2)
Fine and Coarse Ash	0.99
Lapilli	0.88

TABLE IV
EXPECTED ATTENUATION VALUES AT KU- AND KA-BANDS FOR VOLCANIC COMPONENTS.

Volcanic Component	Concentration	Attenuation over 1 km	
		Ku-band 11.72 GHz	Ka-band 19.7 GHz
Fine and Coarse Ash	5 g/m ³	0.06 dB	0.09 dB
	12.15 g/m ³	0.14 dB	0.23 dB
Lapilli	5 g/m ³	0.45 dB	0.87 dB
	12.15 g/m ³	1.12 dB	2.13 dB
Water vapor	5 g/m ³	0.0052 dB	0.054 dB
	30 g/m ³	0.048 dB	0.37 dB

μm .

Fig. 5. Specific attenuation (dB/km) due to water vapor, at 20°C surface temperature for different concentrations, ρ . Data are derived from the ITU-R [2].

V. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE PERSPECTIVE

This study has explored the feasibility of using microwave satellite downlinks for opportunistic tropospheric sensing, aimed at applications in meteorology and geophysics. By examining the interaction between microwave signals and volcanic emissions, we have highlighted the impact of volcanic components on signal attenuation. Considering a volcanic cloud with a thickness of 1 km, Table IV reports the expected attenuation values at Ku- and Ka-bands for different concentrations of the volcanic components. Given that volcanic clouds can have thicknesses of several kilometers, a significantly higher effect is expected, especially for the solid particles. This study offers promising insights for the development and deployment of ground-based sensors, enabling a comprehensive validation of the model through both simulations and experimental measurements. This validation process will be conducted within the framework of Spoke 5 of the SpacItUp project [27], funded by the Italian Space Agency (ASI) and the Italian Ministry for University and Research (MUR), which aims to advance space technology and exploration by integrating various space-related activities.

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